

COMPACTION AND FLUID-STRUCTURE INTERACTION LEADING TO FIBER DISPLACEMENT IN RESIN INFUSION OF COMPOSITE MANUFACTURING

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ABSTRACT

Accurately predicting flow behavior in dry fiber preforms is essential for many liquid molding processes, including resin transfer molding (RTM). One of the main challenges in RTM is obtaining precise permeability values to ensure complete saturation of the preform during infusion. Conventionally, permeability predictions are made using flow experiments on compacted dry fiber layers or by predictive flow simulation assuming an idealised preform. During RTM, the fabric undergoes initial compaction, subsequent relaxation at the arrival of the resin flow front, and eventually full saturation. To address the complex fluid-structure interactions, one approach would be to model the preform deformation during compaction and then study the change in fiber volume fraction during the steady state flow of resin. In this work, a mechanical model accounting for the frictional contact between the yarns was developed in order to predict the displacement during the initial compaction of the dry yarn assembly. The post-compaction deformed geometry is subsequently used within one-way coupled fluid-structure interaction simulations to predict the final fiber distribution within the modelled domain as well as the resultant steady state saturated permeability.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced polymers (FRPs) are known for their high specific strength, excellent stiffness-to-weight ratio and durability, making them ideal for applications across civil infrastructure, aerospace, wind energy, marine, and automotive industries. Vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) is a widely adopted method for manufacturing large-scale composite structures, such as wind turbine blades. In VARTM, resin is infused into a dry fiber preform under near-vacuum conditions by maintaining a small pressure differential between the inlet and the outlet. This slow vacuum-driven infusion, followed by curing in external ovens, eliminates the need for expensive autoclaves. However, VARTM-produced components often exhibit local variations in fiber volume fraction, as the final saturation is influenced by the interplay between the resin's flow capacity (commonly defined by the preform's permeability) and the localized compaction pressure (leading to fiber deformation) [1,2]. The overall permeability of the VARTM mold system, which includes the core, the fiber preform, the distribution media and the peel ply, is affected by the geometric features occurring across multiple scales. At the macro scale (cm to m), elements such as the distribution media, the peel ply, the release film, and the flow channels in the core significantly influence the global resin flow. At the meso-macro scale (mm to cm), the type of weave or the non-woven structure, as well as the lay-up sequence within the laminate, govern how resin propagates through the layers. At the micro-meso scale (μm to mm), factors such as the intra-yarn and the inter-yarn spacing and the packing arrangement become more critical for local permeability. In essence, the macro-scale permeability dictates the resin distribution speed across the mold (helping to prevent large dry spots) while the meso- and the micro-scale permeabilities govern the uniformity of the resin infusion between fibers and the saturation levels (i.e. they impact the inter- and intra-tow micro-void formation).

During VARTM, the dry fiber preform undergoes a sequence of mechanical and fluid interactions beginning with compaction during vacuum bagging, followed by partial relaxation as the resin front

arrives, and concluding with full saturation. These stages introduce complex fluid-structure interactions due to both infusion and compaction effects. Typically, researchers have taken a two-step approach to predict permeability and flow behavior [3]. The first step addresses preform deformation, modeling the yarn's behavior using elastic or hypoelastic properties to capture its deformation during compaction [4] then studying the permeability based on change of fiber volume fraction [5]. Studies have considered fiber displacement due to shear deformation in angle-ply reinforcements [6] due to draping and yarn slippage of woven fiber layups [7], but a significant challenge remains in exporting the predicted deformed geometry to create a fluid domain for flow analysis.

In this study, a model to simulate the yarn deformation and the displacement during the initial compaction of a dry fiber assembly was developed using the mechanical solver within ANSYS Workbench. Realistic boundary conditions corresponding to the vacuum bagging step were applied alongside appropriate contact definitions to prevent yarn interpenetration and to accurately replicate the physical compaction behavior. Following the mechanical simulation, the deformed yarn geometry was transferred to the CFD software ANSYS FLUENT to evaluate the resulting flow behavior and assess the impact on permeability. Key parameters such as the change in global fiber volume fraction (V_f), the yarn slippage, and the potential overlap were analysed to compare the permeability between the undeformed and the compacted configurations of the fiber preform. The use of one-way fluid-structure interaction (FSI) coupling within the unified ANSYS Workbench environment enabled a more refined estimation of both the initial mechanical compaction and the corresponding local flow characteristics to propose more accurate, deformation-dependent permeability predictions.

2 STRUCTURAL MODEL - COMPACTION

The deformation of the fiber layup has been studied in the linear elastic regime (Equation 1) for UD glass fibers considering frictional contact between the yarns. Here, σ and ϵ are the stress and the strain tensor of the material respectively, while the material properties E of the UD fiber correspond to those of Epoxy E-Glass UD with orthotropic elastic properties (Table 1). A static structural analysis is performed in this study while implementing a displacement-based control for the compaction of yarn layups.

$$\sigma = E \epsilon \quad (1)$$

Table 1: Material properties of Epoxy E-Glass UD (Orthotropic) fiber composite.

Epoxy E-Glass UD	Values	Unit
Density (ρ)	2000	kg/m^3
Young modulus X direction (E_x)	45000	MPa
Young modulus Y direction (E_y)	10000	MPa
Young modulus Z direction (E_z)	10000	MPa
Poisson's ratio XY (ν_{xy})	0.3	
Poisson's ratio YZ (ν_{yz})	0.4	
Poisson's ratio XZ (ν_{xz})	0.3	
Shear modulus XY (G_{xy})	5000	MPa
Shear modulus YZ (G_{yz})	3846.2	MPa
Shear modulus XZ (G_{xz})	5000	MPa

Initially an idealised yarn layup consisting of three layers of unidirectional (UD) fibers is placed between two plates. For simplicity, the same frictional contact type has been assumed between the yarns and between the yarn and the mould plate [8], with a friction coefficient value of 0.2. A fixed support was applied to the bottom face of the bottom plate (label A in Figure 1), which fully restrained all translational and rotational degrees of freedom for the bottom plate. The top face of the top plate (label B in Figure 1) was subjected to a displacement of 3mm in the Y-direction. To avoid rigid body motion, the out-of-plane displacement of the yarn side faces across XY plane is set to zero with no translation

along X axis except the translation and compaction along Y-axis (label C in Figure 1). Additionally, on the side face of yarn YZ-plane, the out-of-plane displacement is also set to zero keeping Y-axis free to move (label D in Figure 1). To avoid excessive penetration between the yarns, the pinball radius is set to 0.05mm. The direct numerical scheme with sub-steps control has been considered, thus accounting for over 200 sub-steps allowing large deflection for the yarns. The final displacement of the top plate (0.21 mm) to the maximum allowable distance has been simulated with 3 intermediate displacement load states.

Figure 1: Load state and the boundary conditions for compaction of yarn layup.

Figure 2: Equivalent stress observed on the layup and the compaction plate.

Figure 3: Deformed state of compacted yarn layup and yarns overlap

Figure 2 illustrates the equivalent stresses during the final displacement load state of the top plate. Stress concentrations are visibly evident around the interfaces between the yarn layup, indicating that each yarn experiences substantial mechanical loading as the top plate closes the gap. The symmetrical stress patterns highlight uniformity and periodicity within the internal structure. Figure 3 illustrates the total deformation field in the compacted yarn layups. The central zones, where the yarns are closely packed, exhibit higher deformation magnitudes, suggesting significant compaction induced displacement and mechanical interaction. Additionally, yarn slippage/overlap is also observed between yarn in a layer. These overlapping areas are critical in modeling realistic fiber architecture behavior, as they reflect the actual physical phenomena encountered during manufacturing processes. It is estimated that the global fiber volume fraction V_f increases from 46.54% to 62.55%, while the intra fiber V_f of each yarn is updated from 64% in undeformed configuration to 67.28% (in Table 2) in the deformed state.

Table 2: Change in local intra yarn and global preform fiber volume fraction.

Preform Configuration	Local intra yarn v_f [%]	Global V_f [%]
Undeformed	64	46.54
Deformed	67.28	62.55

3 FLUID MODEL – PERMEABILITY

The compacted yarn layup has been extracted for subsequent CFD simulations to estimate the permeability and predict the flow behaviours. The surface maps of the compacted yarn from the deformed stated are curated to create a suitable mesh for the flow simulation within ANSYS Fluent. It has been assumed that the intra yarn fiber volume fraction (v_f) is 64%. In the Gebert model [9], the micro-scale longitudinal (k_{ll}) and transverse (k_{\perp}) permeability characterization is based on the geometrical arrangement of individual fibers and utilize the fiber diameter and the volume fraction of the yarn. Equation 2, provide the analytical permeability for the hexagonal packing of the individual fiber arrangement in the unit cell of a yarn. Intra-yarn permeability (k_{ll}, k_{\perp}) has been predicted from the Gebert's model considering fibers are arranged in a hexagonal pattern.

$$\begin{aligned}
 k_{ll} &= \frac{8r^2 (1 - v_f)^3}{53 v_f^2} \\
 k_{\perp} &= \frac{16}{9\pi\sqrt{6}} \frac{\left(\sqrt{\frac{v_{fmax_hex}}{v_f}} - 1 \right)^{2.5}}{v_f^2} r^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Here, v_{fmax_hex} refers to the maximum $v_f (= \frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{3}})$ achieved in the hexagonal packing when the circular fiber touches each other within a yarn. A resin with density (ρ) of 1212kg/m³ and viscosity (μ) of 0.09 Pa.s has been used as the fluid medium, with the inlet and the outlet pressure being set at 100 Pa and 10 Pa respectively along the fiber direction of the yarn. A schematic of the flow simulation has been shown in Figure 4.

As depicted in Equation 3, Darcy's law has been used to describe the fluid flow behaviour in the porous media.

$$v = \frac{1}{\mu} \mathbf{K} \cdot (\nabla P + \rho g) \quad (3)$$

where the volume averaged Darcy velocity v was correlated to the pressure gradient ∇P , the dynamic resin viscosity μ , as well as the resin density ρ , through the permeability tensor \mathbf{K} and g the gravitational constant. Moreover, to ensure the resin flow between the porous yarn and the adjacent flow channels, the Brinkmann model has been used. The meso-scale permeability [10] is then estimated based on the calculated flowrate across the outlet surface and the applied pressure gradient between the inlet and the outlet.

Figure 4: Flow configuration of the deformed preform considering porous yarn.

The pressure profiles presented in Figure 5 shows a smooth and continuous gradient from the inlet to the outlet, indicating that a steady-state resin flow has been established in both the undeformed and deformed configurations of the preform. This steady gradient suggests that the flow front has fully propagated through the domain and the pressure distribution has stabilized across the fiber assembly. However, a closer examination of the undeformed configuration reveals that the yarn boundaries near the outlet face exhibit localized pressure variations when compared to the surrounding matrix. This discrepancy may be attributed to the idealized geometry in the undeformed state, where uniform fiber packing and regular channel pathways may not accurately capture the true resin flow resistance encountered at the microstructural level. In contrast, the deformed configuration accounting for the compaction-induced yarn displacement and the change in both the local and the global fiber V_f shows more realistic flow resistance and pressure drop behavior.

Figure 5: Infusion pressure profile in (a) undeformed and (b) deformed state of the preform.

In Figure 6, the velocity profiles during resin infusion through the fiber preform in both the undeformed and deformed states are presented. It is observed that, in the undeformed configuration, the velocity profile reveals significantly higher peak value up to approximately 0.01 m/s in the intra yarn spaces. Thus, the uniform geometry of the undeformed preform, containing relatively large open channels, allows for an easier resin passage. Correspondingly, as shown in Table 3, the undeformed preform exhibits a higher permeability. In contrast, the deformed configuration shows significantly lower flow velocity (around 5.7×10^{-4} m/s) with flow localized along narrower paths. The deformation caused by the mechanical compaction and the yarn displacement altered the internal geometry of the preform, consequently increasing the flow resistance and reducing the overall permeability (by 2-orders of magnitude compared to the undeformed state). From the contour line of velocity profile, it is also noted that level of yarn saturation in the intra yarn porous space is comparatively low in the deformed configuration than the undeformed state.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: Velocity profile in (a) undeformed and (b) deformed state of the preform.

Table 3: Estimated permeability in undeformed and deformed state of preform.

Preform configuration	Global V_f [%]	Permeability [m^2]	Mass flow rate [kg/s]
Undeformed	46.54	1.8572e-10	6.4826459e-07
Deformed	62.55	5.4767e-12	1.3291301e-08

This clearly demonstrates that ignoring the preform deformation can lead to substantial overestimation of flow and permeability. Upon incorporating these deformations, the resulting flow pattern becomes more constrained and non-uniform, better reflecting real manufacturing conditions. These findings emphasize the critical role of coupled fluid-structure interaction modelling in accurately predicting the resin infusion behavior in composite manufacturing processes.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study presents an integrated numerical approach to model compaction-induced deformation and its influence on resin flow in dry fiber preforms during VARTM. By employing a one-way fluid-structure interaction (FSI) framework within ANSYS Workbench, the yarn deformation under mechanical compaction was accurately captured, and the resulting deformed geometry was utilized to simulate the resin flow and predict the permeability. The analysis revealed that compaction significantly alters the internal geometry of the preform, increasing the global fiber volume fraction and reducing the available flow channels, which in turn leads to a substantial decrease in permeability by nearly two orders of magnitude compared to the undeformed configuration. The pressure and the velocity profiles demonstrate that idealized undeformed geometries overestimate the flow uniformity and the resin saturation. It is thus necessary to incorporate the deformation-dependent flow domains within VARTM simulations to enhance the permeability prediction accuracy (and improve the reliability of composite manufacturing process modelling).

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